

SUPPLEMENT C: CO-CLUSTERING FREQUENCIES ON DENSE AND SPARSE MATRICES

Two data files are provided that contain the raw coclustering frequencies of the rows in the sparse and dense data matrices over $N = 2000$ runs. The file format is tab-delimited, and looks like this:

```
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 2000
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (tnf-r2,tnf-r1) 1 36
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (il-2,il-5) 2 7
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (il-11,il-10) 3 8
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (fgf-7,fgf-2) 4 9
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (clopidogrel,p-selectin) 5 25
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (fgf-7,fgf-1) 6 12
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (il-11,il-13) 7 10
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (propranolol,beta2) 8 31
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (isoflurane,caspase-3) 9 400
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (indomethacin,phospholipase) 10 2
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (anti-il-2,cd25) 11 59
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (zuclopenthixol,cyp2d6) 12 13
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (doxycycline,smad7) 13 34
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (il-2,il-1) 14 12
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (corticosteroids,leukotriene) 15 30
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (gliclazide,niddm) 16 16
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (tolbutamide,niddm) 17 26
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (dipyridamole,pde5) 18 3
(flavopiridol,nf-kappab) 0 (geldanamycin,hsp90) 19 0
```

where the order of the columns is:

```
drug-gene-pair-1 numeric-id-1 drug-gene-pair-2 numeric-id-2 cooccurrence-count
```

The names of the two files are:

```
rows-same-cluster-30-125-new.tsv
(results for dense matrix,  $k = 30$ ,  $\ell = 125$ )

rows-same-cluster-fullmatrix-7-25-new.tsv
(results for sparse matrix,  $k = 7$ ,  $\ell = 25$ )
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